

Women Empowerment and Sustainable Development - A Glimpse at Self Help Groups

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Maragatham, RS.

“Women Empowerment and Sustainable

Development - A

Glimpse at Self Help

Groups.” *Shanlax*

International Journal of Arts, Science and

Humanities, vol. 6,

no. S1, 2019,

pp. 205–09.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586427>

R.S.Maragatham

*Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
Justice Basheer Ahmed Sayeed Womens College*

“Mangayarai pirapatharke nalla mathavam sethidal venummamma” I quote Kavimani Desiga Vinayagam Pillai, the great poet of Tamilnadu. His words, keeps ringing like royal drum bells in the mud laden ground of our motherland, where my sisters, you and you and you live, make families, put them into happy homes, cherish and flourish the ties around them. The Kavimani in his poem, celebrates women hood and claims that, “it is nothing but the fruits of hard penance to be born a woman”. The importance of womanhood was thus envisaged decades back, and we are continuously working on her empowerment. This paper is the result of a quick ponder on women empowerment and sustainable development, which will, as a kick back empower the nation. The United nations and the world bank, the world wide organizations working on women’s welfare, are of the view that women’s empowerment is associated with her economic independence and economic empowerment. They result in poverty reduction. We as women, tend to invest more of our earnings in our children and our families.

Decades ago, another great man, The father of our nation, Mahatma Gandhi claimed that “India lives in her villages”. Time and again, our censuses have been proving that statement right. The last census published in the year 2011 quotes 68.84% of Indians, ie about 8.1million people live in about six lakh and 40 thousand villages spread throughout the country. The sex ratio of India, according to the 2011 census is 943 females per 1000 males and the number of females have increased from the last census. This fact reiterates women empowerment, can structure and foster greater economic sustainable development.

As I drive to work every day from home, I am able to foresee that a good size of students of our college will take up employment after their education. While passing by the bus stops and auto stands I see lot of my sisters, immersed in their own plan for the work day, I see empowerment. The flower seller lady, the cobbler amma, morning Idli Kadai akka, and the chat cart akka outside the gates of our college are all pillars of women empowerment. It becomes a mandate to tap the women work force from the grass roots level - the villages.

The economic contribution of Indian women is less than half the global average, whereas china's is at 40 %. A 50 % increase of women workforce in India, could boost India's growth by 1.5 %. (World Bank Publication, March 2018). Keeping in mind the various social, cultural and familial constructs prevailing in India, a 50% increase of women workforce would happen if a industrial revolution is mimicked !! And this can happen if the grassroot level is tapped.

There are a number of initiatives taken by governmental organizations, Nongovernmental organizations, foreign institutions, United nations, public and private companies, women /men unions and women themselves to help themselves become empowered -the self help groups. The self help group projects have supported more than 45 million poor women develop their skills, enter the market and develop businesses of their own. By proving their success in their business ventures, sharing the technical and business acumen, many are role models to others. Empowered women are able to experience better life security, better food for themselves and their family, higher incomes and better financial states. Empowerment in the form of self help groups, also helps in access of low cost financial services, especially with self management and self development of women who are part of the self help group. They are usually connected to banks, which enable their savings culture and access to loan facility. The benefits also cover social, cultural aspects.

Savings of Women in Self Help Groups

Agency	No. of SHG	Saving amount (lakh)
Commercial banks	3'483212	565641,83
Regional Rural Banks	1'753387	139081,96
Cooperatives	1'015079	96565,15
Total	6'251678	801288,94

Source: NABARD 2014

Large Scale Studies on Self Help Groups India

Large scale studies have indicated the sustainability and development of self help groups in India . EDA Rural Systems and APMAS conducted a study "Self Help Groups in India: A Study of the lights and dark sides"- Looking at all aspects of self help groups functioning the study investigated a myriad of topics - membership, maintenance of group records, equity within groups, role of SHGs in local politics, in addressing issues related to social justice and harmony and sustainability of SHGs. The study covered 214 SHGs in nine districts from four states (two each from north and south India) of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Orissa and Rajasthan. Maximum of the members of the self help group were below the poverty line belonging to SC and ST communities. The membership was low due to tough norms followed by the self help groups. But the groups contributed significantly towards social harmony. Another study conducted by NCAER in 2008, assessed the impact of the SHG Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP) to the socio-economic conditions of individual SHG members. It was done in five different regions of India. The pre and post SHG scenarios concluded that the SBLP has positive impact on members by increasing their access to financial services (and reducing household poverty) as well as empowered women through an increase in their self confidence.

Self Help Groups in India and Women Empowerment

In the last few decades, the concept of women empowerment has changed from welfare to equity approach by which the powerless gain control over their lives and resources to overcome external barriers (lack of health, mobility, education and awareness, status in the family, participation in

decision making) and gain internal qualities such as self-awareness and self confidence (Mathew, 2003, p. 24). Self Help groups in India is the worlds largest and most successful community based organization and is predominantly a women’s movement. (K.Raja Reddy and C.S Reddy 2012) India has a large number of self help groups, the major linking force being the nationalized bank, The National bank of agriculture and rural Development (NABARD). This massive movement started in during 1991-1992 when NABARD piloted the SHG-bank linkage program providing access to banking services to poor rural households, especially women. Some NGOs are the leaders in forming the groups. There are financial service promoters who are currently associated with some of the programs. Government has launched projects and schemes of savings and credit to alleviate poverty in the country through self help groups. The 12th five year plan of the Indian government recognizes the importance and relevance of such groups that are useful to implement developmental schemes at the grassroots level for reaching the poor and strengthen their collective capacities. According the 2006 census, more than 33 million women have been linked the banks through various self help groups. There has been a quantum growth, ‘over 400 women per hour’ (NABARD web-site). There is an increase in the number of self help groups in 2006 to 620,000. There are over 9 million women Self help group members. Growth has been strongest in the southern region where Self Help Group and bank linkage first began, with three states (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, and Karnataka) the top three in the country. The south accounts for 54% of SHGs (half of this in Andhra Pradesh alone) and 75% of bank credit. (World Bank, March 2018).

The families in India have to see women as future professionals. A healthy understanding and sharing of household responsibilities between all the members can foster development of women. At the job front, creation and or allocation of suitable jobs, helping in support of child and elderly care, help in movement between workplace, home and care homes will significantly remove operational and structural difficulties in women employment. Curbing difference in wage for men and women, building a support system to curb sexual harassment in work place are some of the steps that workplaces can take for smooth flow of women employment.

Since the 80’s, the SHGs have become a significant movement in India in order to eradicate poverty and empower rural women. Generally these groups are based in poor villages acting as a tool for bringing economic development and contributing to community empowerment (Moeller, 1998, p. 121). This movement has been pointed by many researchers as the model that should be used for poverty reduction (IFAD, 2012). The society in India is predominantly hierarchical society arranged into families, castes and religions. Prevalence of arranged marriage with dowry system, and the bride leaving the house to live in the grooms house is a common feature. The literacy rate of female is about 65.46 % compared to males 82.14%. The age old system of preferring to educate boys more than girls is still prevelant. About 26% of India’s population lives under poverty line.

The self help groups can become a effective tool to eradicate poverty in India, and as a result empower women. 10 to 20 women, belonging to a geographical locality join together and focus on building their financial status by helping each other. They also concentrate and channelize their energies in solving community problems thereby empowering women.

Source: HARPER 2002

There are three models of self help groups - Bank self help group, in which the bank promotes the self help group, Bank facilitating agency self help group, in which NGOs, government agencies or other community based organizations form the groups and Bank, NGO, MFI, self help group in which NGO facilitates and micro finances intermediaries. The self help group is created in four stages, stage one being social mobilization and formation of groups, second being savings and internal lending among members of groups, third being obtaining micro finance and the fourth being setting micro enterprises. The self help groups are characterized by 10 -20 members, one member from one family, one gender in a group, similar social and financial background and attendance at meetings.

The self help groups are beneficial and are an important vehicle of women empowerment in India because of the following reasons. They alleviate poverty and increase employment opportunity. This accelerates economic growth and raises the status of the women and that family in the society. It increases the income generation methods, thereby creating fresh jobs and increases the feeling of common brotherhood. It helps in decreasing domestic violence.

Region	Number of SHG			Total
	Commercial Banks	RRB	Cooperatives	
Northern	11.444	4.843	7.631	23.918
North Eastern	5.323	10.524	354	16.201
Eastern	87.865	73.247	136.366	297.478
Central	28.074	36.007	2.312	66.393
Western	43.683	12.330	31.833	87.846
Southern	590.864	196.469	87.252	874.585
Total	767.253	333.420	265.748	1'366.421

Source : NABARD 2014

A few success stories of self help group have been listed below

1.RIDE NGO: This cluster of self help groups were started in Musaravakkam , in Tamilnadu. The village has more than 4500inhabitants and has close to 35 self help groups, many of them working as a separate financial unit. Various businesses that could happen in a village are under the perview of these self help groups. Milk vending, basket making, sanitary napkin making, mop making are some of the lucrative business that happen under the umbrella of this self help group. Sales for their products happen at various cities across India. This group has been selected by NABARD as an excellent society and thanks to this award, its financing bank will offer an extra economic support for their activities (RIDE, 2015).

2. PRADAN NGO formed in Alwar, Rajasthan in the year 1987 This self help group speaks about the success on a single woman, who started her puffed rice business with a loan of Rs200. She has diversified into vegetable cultivation and milk business. Her profits have helped her son get education from a school in a town nearby her village. She makes it a compulsion to save on a weekly basis. She is more than a proof of how self help groups can empower women. In 2013, PRADAN worked with 18736 SHGs across 7 states with a total membership of 252.070 rural poor women saving around Rs. 1230 million (PRADAN, 2015). SHG in India Source: Professional Assistance for Development Action, 2015.

3. In a study conducted by Goankar et al, in Goa state, it was found that the family income increased. Improved self confidence and productive use of free time were other benefits. In a nutshell, the members felt a improvement in the quality of lives (Gaonkar, 2001, p. 78).

4. Another study by Prasad et al reported that more than 90% of women learnt to write their names and do simple arithmetic (Prasad, 2000, p. 35).

5. Kothai found an increase in self confidence of members. She found that women were able to go to banks without the help of the men. (Kothai, 2008, p. 45).

However, there are some studies which point out problems of self help groups like the lack of cooperation, lack of support from organizations, ineffective group leadership, lack of training in group formation, mismanagement on accounts, time constraints, lack of decision making, inadequate space to conduct activities, lack of uniform growth, lack of marketing intelligence for the new products, and lack of information when needed (Leelavathi & Aradhana, 2006, p. 25).

In the end, Indian women themselves will play a key role in claiming a space for themselves in India's work force. Personally, I will continue to advocate for them. I hope you will join me.

Let's all pledge together today to increase women's participation in the work force, and realize a higher level of growth and development for India that is more inclusive and sustainable.

References

1. NABARD, annual report 2013-2014, Mumbai, India.
2. IFAD. 2003: Empowering Women Through Self-Help Microcredit Programmes. Bulletin on Asia-Pacific Perspectives 2002/03.
3. Anjugam, M. and Ramasamy, C. 2007: Determinants of Women's participation in Self-Help Group led micro finance programme in Tamil Nadu. Agricultural Economics Research Review, 2007, vol. 20, issue 2.
4. Haider, Rumel, Akhtar and Rasheda. 1999: The role of NGO and women's perception of empowerment: An anthropological study in a village. Empowerment, vol. 6.
5. Kishor, S., Gupta, K. 2009: Gender equality and women's empowerment in India. National Family Health Survey India. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.